

ISic3511

Epitaph for Klodia Romana

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Katherine Backler,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2017.07.20 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Found within a funerary building within the area designated 'recinto B' by Paolo Orsi during excavation in 1914 of the

Coordinates

38.1992517, 15.5566385

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3568

Physical Description

An intact marble tablet, uneven on the left and upper borders, with minor damage to the lower left corner

Dimensions

Height 21 cm
Width 26.8 cm
Depth 1.8-2.2 cm

Layout

Five lines of Greek text, observing a regular left margin, with hedera in the four corners

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Somewhat irregular letters, tending to cursive (e.g. mu), and often leaning to the left; omega, sigma and epsilon all lunate in form; theta a circle with an unconnected central bar; triangular letters tend to have a slightly extended top stroke.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: 22-28 mm
Line 5: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation lines 1 to 5: 10-13 mm

Text

1. Θ(εοῖς)(vac.undefin)Δ(αίμοσιν)
2. Κλωδία
3. Ῥωμάνα
4. ἔζησε ἔ
5. τη λε

6. (vac. undefined)

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 and photograph.

Translation (en)

To the divine spirits. Klodia Romana lived 35 years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493841

EDCS 38200002

PHI 313627

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 4

Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 134 fig.9

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